

DO WE NEED NATURE?

Gamil M. El-Taliawi, Ph.D. (Columbia University)

Professor Of Chemistry
Faculty of Pharmacy, Cairo University
Cairo, Egypt

Synopsis:

This question reflects a deeply seated crisis in our perception of nature and where exactly is the position of man with respect to it. For two centuries, man established himself as a conqueror of nature and harnessed it fully, disregarding the fact that he is an integral part of it. As a result, our natural web is suffering great stresses. This essay throws light on our Hellenistic heritage that precipitated antagonism between humanism and nature. It emphasizes the healthy approach of man to nature, learning from it rather than aggressing against. The natural wisdom of producing what is recyclable and biodegradable is a great lesson to man. However, we must reconsider the fabrics of our civilization, including our materialistic and exploitative attitudes, our norms of production and consumption and our extreme individuality and our irrational order of priorities. The energy dilemma stands as an example of our lack of vision of ecologically sound alternatives. In the process of photosynthesis, green plants harvest solar energy very efficiently and convert it into beneficial products that are recyclable and finally biodegradable. What if we learn from nature? Just as we learned from the primitive *Penicillium* fungi that produced natural penicillin and became able to design highly effective antibiotics against pathogenic microbes, we ought to change our means of production so as to adapt it to nature. Genetic engineering expands our horizons of emulating nature. Gene therapy of heredity diseases is revolutionizing our capacity to handle our health problems. But the greatest artificial in our lives is our modern lifestyle. Our isolation from nature and lack of interaction with its most important ingredient, light, may compromise our immune system in its struggle with virulent agents.

Thus, instead of collision with nature, our current civilization must be evolved such that it adapts itself to nature.

DO WE NEED NATURE?

This question reflects the very deep crisis in which we find ourselves muddled in. Are “we” the human species becoming so oblivious to nature to the extent that such a question is raised? Yet, this is a real question and the gravity of its relevance entitles us to discuss our relationship to nature fully, so that subtle issues that keep popping up be settled satisfactorily.

But what is this nature that we speak of? Isn't it the vast life continuum that spreads from the smallest virus that may be so virulent, to the giant whales that swim so gracefully in the oceans? Isn't it the highly sophisticated web that integrates living and non-living beings inhabiting the universe? Doesn't it include the great forests and the vast oceans, the little valleys and the overpowering mountains?

In the past two centuries, it has been amply demonstrated that all beings, living and non-living, are so interdependent that any perturbation of their equilibrium can be catastrophic and devastating to all. Interestingly, whenever one examines the relationships between members of this web, you discover that a certain law governs them. Doesn't this reflect the meticulous workings of a Supreme Creator who calculated everything such that this highly intricate web is well sustained and harmoniously maintained? This natural perfection necessarily invalidates the false assumption that nature is accidental, chaotic and random in its inception. If we sink deeply in our subconscious, we shall discover the old remnants of our Hellenistic polytheistic attitudes. Wasn't Prometheus the one who stole the “divine fire” from the gods while they were asleep, brought it to earth and gave it to mankind? Of course, this angered the gods and started the millennia-old antagonism between humanism and the rule of gods. These gods were of course the archetypes of nature. The forces of nature symbolized by this mythology involve the seas, rivers, earth, rain, physical strength as well as storms, earthquakes, illness, drought and so forth. Thus, man must strive to conquer these forces. And what is his tool? The divine fire or what we now call science and technology. This is the battle in which man became a conqueror and nature was to be conquered.

Thus, for two centuries, man has been exploiting his environment, disregarding the fact that he is an integral part of it and whose very existence depends upon. We have been harnessing nature to the fullest with undue regard to its health and welfare.

Therefore, the first step towards a healthy relationship between man and nature is to purify our intellect from this mythological pollution. In addition, we must modify our extremely materialistic and exploitative vision of nature. Of course, for this to take place, we need to reconsider the fabrics of our current civilization. So far, nature has been adapted to consumption demands of growing economies. Since our ecosystem is coming under great pressures as a result, wouldn't it be wise that our current civilized existence be made adaptable to existing natural constraints?

Since the advent of the industrial revolution, our economies have been revolving around a central core that dictates production and consumption. So we produce in order to consume and consume more in order to produce far more. And the products that we make are becoming much less enduring such that the new keeps out placing the worn old. This vicious circle must be addressed if we ever hope of healing our natural ecosystem. Besides, our norms of behavior are highly individualistic and we think less of collective norms. For example, we rely less on mass transit systems that are less polluting and depend more on automobiles that are highly polluting. Furthermore, our order of priorities is highly disproportionate. Take for instance the case of the military industrial complex. It has been producing the most elaborate

machines to kill, with huge amounts of wealth spent, yet the wealth invested to address human and environmental development is much far less. This lack of rational behavior on the part of governments must be corrected if we ever hope of transacting reconciliation with nature.

And in the field of energy, consider the dilemma that is facing the world. On one hand, fossil fuels like petroleum and coal are extensively polluting our atmosphere and current levels of carbon dioxide emissions are warming the globe to the extent that the polar ice caps are beginning to melt. The extent of devastation to continental shores is anybody's guess. On the other hand, nuclear energy is not a wise alternative. Not only because of the environmental hazards involved, but the radioactive waste disposal in deep under ground salt beds would, in the long run, pollute water reservoirs and rivers with highly carcinogenic leakages. Why don't we learn from nature instead and see how do green plants photo-synthetically harvest solar energy and convert it silently into beneficial products? Learning from nature's wisdom, one may dream of a day when the vast expanses of the sunny areas of the world become fields of harvesting solar photons, using efficient photovoltaic cells, and the energy captured be transported across the globe. Wouldn't this be environmentally sound and help heal our ecosystem?

Another lesson that we need to learn from nature is its wisdom of making products that are both recyclable and finally biodegradable. Consider how man-made synthetic polymeric fibers, nylon and plastics, are becoming an environmental nightmare. Because of its resistance to recycling and biodegradability, it is transforming our landscape into a rapidly expanding dumpsite. Wouldn't it be better to emulate nature and learn how to make synthetic fibers that insert structural fragments in its makeup such that it becomes biodegradable? Of course this is a chemical challenge, but our chemical knowledge is currently fully mature.

Furthermore, becoming a student of nature is not something adventitious. When the natural penicillins, produced by simple fungal creatures were discovered, we learned a great deal from the genius of these fungi. We became able to make antibiotics that are broad spectrum and have greater potencies against pathogenic microbes. In fact, a student of pharmaceutical chemistry would tell you that most of our today's arsenal of drugs has their origins in natural products produced by medicinal plants and members of the animal kingdom.

However, the fear of the "artificial" does not substantiate any case against genetic engineering that involves genetic modifications of crops, to increase its yields and make it immune to damaging parasitic infections. This fear is understandable in view of the fact that long term effects of genetically modified foods on human health are still convincingly unsettled. But like with new drugs and medicaments, long-term research must be performed before their marketing to ascertain their safety. Therefore, it is unwise to condemn genetic modifications altogether under fearful pretexts. Genetic engineering nonetheless proved remarkably valuable in producing insulin, via its use of recombinant DNA technology. Thus, artificiality in genetic modifications is rationally unjustified. In fact, gene therapy of hereditary diseases is revolutionizing our ability to correct biological malfunctions. This therapy replaces a wrong gene with a correct one. As we know, every gene is responsible for the production of a specific protein. So, if the health problem is corrected by gene replacement, would this be any different as a therapy, from the administration of an antidepressant drug for instance to a patient suffering from mental depression and alleviating his pain via increasing the level of his brain amines? Mechanistically, gene therapy is different. But philosophically, it is similar. Again, the fear of extrapolating man's ability to play

with genes is premature at best. However, cloning of humans is an entirely different matter. Naturally, an offspring gets half his chromosomes from the mother and gets the other half from the father. Thus, nature promotes biodiversity that enriches the great genetic pool and enhances man's ability to adapt to his ever-changing environment. By contrast, cloning fabricates an exact replica, thus eliminating biodiversity. It is not only anti-natural, but is anti-ethical as well, since it victimizes what it fabricates. This is the most flagrant of man's violations of natural laws.

But the greatest "artificial" in our lives is our modern lifestyle. The great cities of the world are ornamented with giant skyscrapers, inside which many human beings work in artificially lit offices and in complete isolation from natural light. After work, they house themselves in homes that further their compartmentalization. It is estimated that in Los Angeles, people spend an average of only four hours outdoors every twenty-four hours. Thus, we deprive ourselves of the healthy interaction with nature and its most important ingredient, light. Many of us are unaware that collision with the natural light/dark cycle leads to many health problems. Latest research in biology and medicine have unraveled the intimate connection between secretion of melatonin, a master hormone produced by the pineal gland, and interaction with natural light. The relationship between melatonin concentration in our blood and the abilities of our immune system, among many other things, is well established. This is the system that protects us against bacteria, viruses, cancer and Alzheimer's disease, to say the least. This argument stands firmly against advocates of independence from nature.

But no one may underestimate the complexity of the required change that must be made in order to save our natural web. And no one can ignore the forces that would array themselves to oppose it. However, it is a great battle for the survival of the human species on this planet. Already one can hear the voices of activist groups across the globe pushing for the change. This evolution in our civilization should be catalyzed by our love of nature and our determined efforts to save it and learn from it.

And to speak of sustainable growth that is friendly to the environment while preserving the current methodologies of production and consumption, is frankly deceptive. Unless we bring about fundamental changes in our means of production and adapt our products to nature, sustainable growth will become unsustainable to the environment.

In conclusion, man must strive to integrate himself with nature and interact positively with its rhythmic forces. This should be the natural evolution of our civilization in this millennium.

So, do we need nature? The answer is most emphatically, yes.